

DEVELOPING A STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR INTEGRATING LANGUAGE SKILLS THROUGH TECHNOLOGY-SUPPORTED LESSONS.**Author: Nozima Abduhalilova**

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Abstract

techforeign educators in combining multi-linguistic skills through technology-supported lessons in basic school. The given framework contains four main stages: 1) Skill mapping, 2) digital tool distribution, 3) lesson flow representing, 4) integrating evaluation. “A quasi-experimental method was used to identify whether training instructors to utilize given framework in order to enhancing children`s attendance” [5,12]. In these experiment two groups of Grade 2 pupils (ages 7-8) took part in the three-week research, the experimental group (n= 15) was guided be their English teacher using the strategic framework, in comparison, the control group (n= 15) get regular lessons but it was without structured organized and planned techniques. Both groups learned similar vocabulary, speaking and reading assignments supported by technologies and short instructional videos.

Key words: strategic framework, integration of skills, digital tools, primary education, technology-supported instructions, English language teaching.

1.Introduction

Nowadays technology integration is becoming a center to modern language teaching, especially it is essential in primary education, where children ask visual support, drills, and interactive approaches. Moreover, digital tools are widely using by educators to struggle integration skills. “Without well- organized schedule, technologies can improve enrollment, however, decries the number of learners” [3,12].

Previous researches emphasize the requirement for structured planning examples that assist educators distinguish which skills to improve, which tools to utilize, and how to organize their lesson and plan of the lesson effectively. However, there are some limitations on empirical evidence of framework for young learners.

The main aim of this study is to address this gap by advancing a 4-stage framework for language integration of English skills via technology-assisted lessons and examining its value in real classroom situations.

Questions to research:

1. Does the strategic framework improve learner's speech and reading comprehension?
2. Does it help more systematic language skills?

2.Methods

A quasi-experimental design was chosen to show the efficiency of the given framework for organizing technology-supported course. The study shows two group of participants: first one is an experimental group exposed to strategic framework to improve speaking and reading skills and the second one is a control group receiving traditional learning system. "Assignment was not in random position due to administrative rules, thus intact classes we used during the whole process" [2.15].

2.1 Participants.

Thirty children aged 7-8 (grade 2) took part in our experiment, they were named to:

*Experimental group (n=15)- where educators organize the framework (strategic)

*Control group (n=15)- teacher will utilize traditional techniques according to tasks without organizing main plan.

2.2 The strategic framework

Stage 1: Skill mapping-teacher finds desired achievements for instance speaking and reading sections.

Stage 2: Digital tool distribution- technologies used while research:

* short videos > context of the reading

* applications for recording voice > speaking preparation

* interactive tools > for supporting vocabulary

Stage 3: lesson flow representing

Clear sections: input > study > creation

Stage 4: integrating evaluation

Effective and quick quizzes from Kahoot or from other tools for speaking.

2.3 Procedure

Duration of the practice is 3 weeks, lesson is organized 3 times per week, and 30 minutes each. The same topics and exercises had both 1st group (experimental) and 2nd (control) "My holiday and my hobbies", while using appropriate tablets and watching related videos.

The 1st group followed the framework consisted of 4 stages.

The 2nd group used tool freely without planning.

2.4 Instruments

Based on reading testing system where were 10 comprehension exercises with small texts and speaking integration to make in advance level: fluency, vocabulary acquisition, pronunciation, maximum score was 20 points.

3.Results

3.1 Test scores

Table 1 –results of pre-test and post-test

Skill	Group	Pre-test mean	Post-test mean	Improvements %
Reading	Experimental	8.1	12.6	+55.6%
	Control	8.8	9.9	+12.5%
Speaking	Experimental	10.3	14.8	+43.7%
	Control	11.1	12.7	+14.6%

As we can see in this table, the experimental group demonstrated higher test results in both speaking and reading integration skills, while in control group were lower gains in two skills.

3.2 Qualitative observations

By teachers was given- 1) clear and understandable structures lesson preparation time. 2) learning process demonstrated more participation during our research. 3) using online tools were appropriately.

4.Discussion

The results of the test illustrated that the strategic framework aid educators to improve both two main skills like reading and speaking more functionally. Children in the 1st group gained better results due to well-organized instructional plan which ensured good results. The 2nd group also tried to do their best and they also enhanced, but a bit less percentage of improvement in gains, supposing that digital instruments alone do not ensure effective learning unless guided by strategic framework.

These findings corroborate with previous experimentations that digital instruments ask pedagogical plan to advance impact. This study illustrates evidence from junior classes an area where planning the lessons plays an integral role. Restrictions include a small representative size and temporary duration. “Future studies ought to implement the framework over a semester and explore more combinations of integrated skills” [1.5].

5. Conclusion

The strategic framework demonstrated usefulness for enhancing reading understanding and fluency between learners. Teachers utilizing the framework illustrated more standardized integration of skills resulted use of digital platforms. The research comments acquiring structured framework examples while organizing technology-supported lessons.

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